

BIOServices

Linking soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services in different land uses: from the identification of drivers, pressures, and climate change resilience to their economic valuation

Title: Ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data

Deliverable: D7.1

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Report

Document summary

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Executive summary

This deliverable meets the ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data, in particular: 1) the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit participants; 2) the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participants and in regard to data processing; 3) templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation and data protection issues; 4) the contribution of BIOservicES to all the environment objectives included in the Do Not Harm Principles; 5) the adherence of BIOservicES to the ethical principles defined by the EC for artificial intelligence; 6) clarification of how all personal data that will be processed are relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project (in accordance with the 'data minimisation' principle); 7) a description of the technical and organisational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants; 8) a description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing; 9) description of the pseudonymisation techniques that will be implemented; 10) The activities undertaken outside the EU and 11) the materials imported to EU and exported from the EU.

These requirements will be achieved via the introduction of different measures during data collection, storage, retention, and destruction. In addition, it includes justifications for personal data transfer between EU and non-EU countries and procedures for the handling of incidental collection of personal data due to the use of drones and satellite imagery.

BIOservicES Consortium includes eight EU and three non-EU countries (Switzerland, USA and UK). Switzerland is involved in the WPs 1, 2, 4, 6 and 7; USA is involved in the WPs 1, 2, 6 and 7; and UK is involved in the WPs 1, 3, 4, 6 and 7 of BIOservicES project. That means that they will participate in the recruitment of the stakeholders, in the collection of the information from the recruited participants, in the treatment, storage and destruction of that information, also in the development of activities in the experimental sites and the treatment of the collected soil samples.

1. Regulations used for the preparation of this deliverable.

The following regulations were used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework

Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013 (Text with EEA relevance).

- Directive (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation.
- Article 14 Grant Agreement Model.
- EU Grants: How to complete your ethics self-assessment: V2.0 – 13.07.2021.
- EU grants: Classification of information in Horizon Europe projects: V1.0 – 22.07.2021.
- EU Grants: How to handle security-sensitive projects: V1.0 – 01.07.2021;
- Ethics Advisor and Ethics Advisory Boards: v2.0 – 15.02.2023.
- Horizon Europe - Ethics Advisor / Ethics Advisory Board Report - Version 1.5 - March 2023.
- European Textbook on Ethics in Research.
- Ethics for researcher – Facilitating Research Excellence (European Commission).
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Ethics in Social Science and Humanities (European Commission).
- Research, risk-benefit analysis and ethical issues (European Commission).
- Guidance to facilitate the implementation of targets to promote gender equality in research and innovation (European Commission).
- Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans (European Commission).

2. Procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit participants.

BIOservicES will engage multiple stakeholders with potential interest in the role of soil biodiversity in the provision of key soil ecosystem functions and services (EFS), via interesting and relevant/targeted activities through meetings, workshops, focus groups, surveys, and in-person interviews. These activities will facilitate interactions between scientists, farmers, advisors, consumers, policymakers, certification specialists, foresters, industries, miners, entrepreneurs, investors, consumers, public authorities, EU and international organisations and initiatives, etc. BIOservicES will create bridges and establish a dialogue between the researchers and stakeholders, developing a mutual understanding of how different people work and think, also facilitating open and transparent research. Minors will not participate in BIOservicES activities.

Participants will be identified and recruited by the WP1 leaders (LGI and Zabala) in collaboration with all partners, especially with other WP leaders and

experimental site leaders. They must conduct the recruitment in a manner consistent with ethical considerations:

- Respect of autonomy for privacy
- Lack of pressure or undue influence, since the participation in the study is entirely voluntary, the participating individuals will not obtain any occupational advantage and the non-participating individuals will not have penalty on the job or any other negative consequence.
- Accurate and clear description of the project
- Unbiased presentation of the project

Participants will be identified and recruited through various procedures. Indirect recruitment methods will include public advertisement via the webpage, social media, information boards at different types of potential stakeholder organizations, etc. More direct tools and methods to approach audiences will be personalized e-mails, telephone calls, and presentations to community groups or face-to-face meetings. Focusing on individuals or groups who have the potential to reach and attract a greater number will be a priority in communications.

3. Informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participants and data processing.

Each participant in any of the BIOServicES activities (surveys, in-person interviews, workshops, events, sampling with ge positioning data, etc.) shall be requested to sign an informed consent form. The consent document will be used as a guide for a more detailed verbal explanation of the BIOServicES project. The consent document will be the basis for a meaningful exchange between the researcher and the participant. The participant's signature will provide documentation of agreement to participate in a study, but it is only one part of the consent process. The consent document will not serve as a substitute for discussion.

Information about the project will be prepared in an appropriate form and language for potential participants, catering to the audience's needs. This will include rules for participation and withdrawal from participation. Partners will ensure the translation of materials into regional/national languages. Furthermore, participants should be given sufficient time to decide on the requested consent.

Participants shall be informed that they are free to withdraw from participation at any point, that their personal data will remain confidential and anonymous, and that collected data will be analysed for the entire subgroup of participants rather than individually, thus securing their privacy and anonymity.

Detailed information shall be provided to the potential participants employing an information sheet including descriptions/specifications of:

- purpose of the research
- purpose of the participation
- duration of the research activities
- voluntary participation
- possible risks, discomfort or disadvantages
- benefits to the subject or others
- data protection, confidentiality and privacy policies
- destination of the data, samples and results at the end of the research
- where to get more information

4. Template of the informed consent/assent form and information sheets

Title of the project: LINKING SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONS AND SERVICES IN DIFFERENT LAND USES: FROM THE IDENTIFICATION OF DRIVERS, PRESSURES AND CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE TO THEIR ECONOMIC VALUATION (HORIZON project 101112374)

Project Coordinator: Raúl Zornoza, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena

Regional Coordinator: [Name, Institutional affiliation]

Institution responsible for the research / Contact information:

[Partner Institution] is the controller of your personal data. You may contact [Partner Institution] at [Address] or by phone and e-mail at: [Insert Name and Contact Info of Person in Unit Requesting Personal Data].

About BIOServicES Project: BIOServicES project (funded by Horizon Europe) will provide new knowledge about the soil ecosystem functions and services associated to soil organisms and develop new indicators, tools and incentives to identify and monitor the keystone soil organisms that contribute to the delivery of ecosystem services in European land uses. BIOServicES will also provide an economic valuation of the ecosystem services in which soil organisms contribute, together with different private and public policy and economic incentive tools. The consortium integrates a multi-actor approach for including the different perspectives of stakeholders to decision-makers that regulate and administer policies.

Types of participation.

You are invited to participate in our research study on how soil organisms are involved in the delivery of ecosystem functions and services under the BIOServicES project. You will be requested to participate in:

- Questionnaires
- In-person interviews
- Co-creation workshops
- In video/audio recording about your experience as a stakeholder
- Focus Groups
- Permission to collect soil/plant samples from your field
- Permission to implement experimental sites in your field

- Dissemination events
- Others (specify):

Time involvement: This research study may take up to approximately five years after your participation.

Risks and benefits: The risks associated with this study can be: SELECT (economic or associated to impacts on profits and safety, data protection, data management, privacy or reputation). We cannot and do not guarantee or promise that you will receive any benefits from this study. Your decision whether or not to participate in this study will not affect your participation in other BIOServicES events and activities.

Payment: You will not receive any reimbursement as payment for your participation.

Use of data/samples: The materials and data collected will become part of studies that may be presented at scientific meetings or published in scientific journals, non-scientific meetings, non-scientific journals for communication and dissemination purposes of BIOServicES project. Personal Data shall be processed only for those administrative, operational, accounting, research and monitoring purposes necessary for the safe and reliable implementation of BIOServicES, without prejudice to the individual rights under the relevant laws.

Personal data collected during the study:

Demographic Data: Country and region, age, gender, education level

Professional: Job position, education, membership, seniority, description of company.

Confidentiality: Your responses/interventions will be kept confidential. At no time will your actual identity be revealed. You will be assigned a random numerical code. Anyone who helps in the transcription of the responses will only know you by this code. Any other person outside the Project team will not analyse your responses/interventions, location, etc. The recording will be destroyed as soon as it becomes unnecessary or 5 years after the project is terminated. The transcript will be kept without your name until the research is complete.

Audiotape: Your participation could be voluntarily audio-taped. You will not be asked to state your name on the recording. The tapes will only be heard by the interviewer and/or other members of the BIOServicES project team for transcription purposes and will never be publicly accessible. If you feel uncomfortable with the recorder, you may ask to be turned off anytime.

Data storage, protection, retention and destruction: Personal Data will be stored on private media securely owned by the project members or the consortium to prevent confidentiality breaches during the project's period and beyond the project's lifetime. The data will be completely erased immediately after you ask us for it. Otherwise, your personal data will be erased automatically, at last, in August 2033, five years after the end of the project.

Your data could be shared with other member/s of the BIOservicES consortium. The list of the members can be consulted at www.bioservices.eu.

Your Rights: Under the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you have the right to request access to, rectify, erase and restrict the processing of your personal data. You also have the right to revoke this consent to use your personal data. Your participation is voluntary and you have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw your participation, samples or data at any time without any consequences. You must contact [Partner Institution] by phone or e-mail to exercise those rights. Your name and contact data will permanently be retained confidential, will never be made public, findable or accessible, and you will never be identified or linked to the samples or data. You will permanently be the owner of the data and samples collected. The data will be accessible to you in a personal communication and/or report.

However, if you feel that [Partner Institution] does not answer you properly when exercising your rights or the [Partner Institution] has violated European Law, you can file a complaint with the appropriate EU supervisory authority.

Participation and withdrawal: Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You may withdraw by informing the experimenter that you no longer wish to participate (no questions will be asked, without penalty or negative consequences). You may skip any question during the interview but continue participating in the rest of the study.

Contact information: If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, contact the Project Coordinator (Dr. Raúl Zornoza; raul.zornoza@upct.es; +34 868 071 130). Add your Regional Coordinator contact information.

Independent contact: If you are not satisfied with how this study is being conducted, or if you have any concerns, complaints, or general questions about the research or your rights as a participant, please contact Mr Francisco Javier Castro (ethical advisor) from Ethical & Legal Plus S.L. (fcastro@plusethics.com, +34 602 13 60 85, www.plusethics.com) to speak to someone independent of the research team.

Coordinator Data Protection Officer (DPO): dpd@upct.es; RSC DPO: **ADD your RSC DPO information.**

You are encouraged to ask questions or raise concerns at any time about the nature of the study or the methods.

Please, select YES or NO:

I consent to participate in the activity/ies listed in the section “purpose of your participation” in the present document.

YES NO

I consent that my personal data will be used for the purposes stated in this document for the BIOServicES project and will be always anonymous and never accessible.

YES NO

I consent that the interview will be recorded during the event/meeting and used inside the BIOServicES project.

YES NO

I consent to be photographed during the event/meeting and used inside the BIOServicES project.

YES NO

Participant's Name:

Place and Date

Signature

5. Do Not Harm Principles (DNHP)

BIOservicES will contribute substantively to all the environment objectives included in the DNHP: 1) Climate change mitigation and adaptation through restoration of soil EFS, involving C sequestration and storage and reduced GHG emissions. 2) Sustainable use and protection of water through restoring soil EFS, which contributes to increase clean water resources. 3) Transition to a circular economy through investments to recover degraded soils by sustainable strategies. 4) Pollution prevention and control through practices and initiatives focused to restore soil health by with management that fosters soil biodiversity. 5) Protection and restoration of biodiversity through management that restores soil health with high above- and below ground biodiversity, considering the lowest impact possible by our sampling approaches and by the reduction of the CO2 footprint with a single shipment with all soil samples from each partner.

6. Artificial Intelligence

BIOservicES project adheres to the ethical principles defined by the EC for artificial intelligence of (1) Respect of human autonomy, (2) Prevention of harm, (3) Fairness and (4) Explicability. Software will be developed using Open Source languages (R and Python). BIOservicES strictly focuses on providing computing tools to assist human decision-making, securing human oversight and freedom, protection and cyber-security. The tools developed will not entail any impact to human dignity, mental or physical integrity, neither will they promote situations of power or information asymmetries. In addition to this, artificial intelligence systems will: (i) guarantee privacy and data protection, (ii) be explainable and open in the communication about their limitations, (iii) be user-centric and be usable by different types of end-users with different abilities and (iv) avoid possible risks of damage to societal and environmental well-being.

No personal data will be collected, and the source code of the software will be Open Access with detailed documentation, ensuring transparency. Users will be informed that they are accessing artificial intelligence technology. The calculation methods will be included in scientific articles to provide explicability on the results of the computational. Fairness and explicability will be further included in communication and dissemination activities during the

project life (<https://www.aepd.es/sites/default/files/2019-12/ai-ethics-guidelines.pdf>).

7. Description of the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of participants and environment.

BIOservicES shares the principle of safeguarding the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants following the EU's 2016/679 GDPR. BIOservicES partners are aware of the need to protect the personal data collected during the project, to guarantee the legal framework in publishing results and in general, to protect the rights of individuals.

All the security measures commonly implemented by each partner for the protection of digital and/or physical data are expected to cover the data of the BIOservicES project. Besides, the following measures have been specifically established in the frame of the BIOservicES project, which will be shared and mandatory for all the partners:

7.1. Data collection

Informed consent will be used to recruit research participants (see section 3 of this Deliverable). Participants will also be informed about their rights to request access to, be informed, object, blocking, file a complaint, damages, data portability, rectify, erase and restrict the processing of their personal data at any moment during the project's development and until the data are entirely erased. Stakeholders' participation in surveys, interviews, workshops and other events is voluntary; the participants can decide to participate in the whole activity or just partly (i.e., answering just the questions they decide to answer).

Based on the data minimization principle, BIOservicES will only collect the personal data that are adequate and necessary exclusively for this project, i.e., simple contact data (i.e., full name, address, telephone and/or email, only if needed for future contact), personal data (i.e., age, gender, level of studies, titles), and other data (i.e., location of the field, field management, etc.), required to fulfil the aims of the project, strictly necessary to achieve any given specific task or purpose for which they are collected, i.e. BIOservicES will only collect the data needed to meet the research objectives. Moreover, project data will be periodically analysed to erase information that is not relevant to the project.

7.2.Data storage

Each partner of the consortium will be responsible for the data storage during the research project's lifetime, and no personal data will be transferred among partners of the BIOservicES project or with third parties. Before data are stored, they will be **systematically pseudonymised** via data masking (scientific and personal data will be codified, separated and stored in different files) to prevent possible identification of personal data from experimental sites and/or individuals' opinions or ideas. The pseudonymization of data (via masking technique) will allow BIOservicES to work daily only with no personal data preventing unauthorized access to personal data. The scientific data (not personal) will be stored and shared between BIOservicES partners for project development via BIOservicES members' emails and the BIOservicES SharePoint (Microsoft365 TEAMS) handled by UPCT. The use of Microsoft Office 365 TEAMS will ensure that all data files are kept for BIOservicES consortium use despite problems in personal computers. Microsoft protects the Microsoft Office 365 TEAMS from viruses and data piracy. This will help to ensure the security of the data held on computers used in the project. In fact, some activities will be directly performed online on files stored on Microsoft Office 365 TEAMS to ensure that the last version of the document is the one saved on the system and shared by all partners that may need it.

Some of the security measures addressed in the BIOservicES project are listed below:

1. Implement additional information and transparency measures for the data subject.
2. Cancel the data as soon as they are no longer necessary for the purpose of processing.
3. Delimit the social or economic contexts in which the processing will be applied.
4. The data subject is always aware of when data are processed.
5. Eliminate secondary purposes in the processing.
6. Assess the need and limit the set of personal data collected.
7. Avoid cross-referencing data with other information on data subjects.
8. Avoid unnecessary processing of personal data (in particular, special categories of data).
9. Training of partners to detect possible misconduct.

10. Train partners on the private use of the organization's tools.
11. Guarantee deadlines for exercising rights in real-time or shorter than those established in art. 12 of the GDPR.
12. Ensure that the consequences of erroneous processing of the data subject's impact are reversible.
13. Ensure that private spheres are not invaded.
14. Implement agile methods and effects for reporting problems.
15. Implement access control on a need-to-know basis.
16. Include transparency actions towards stakeholders regarding the use of these systems.
17. Include in the data protection policy procedures for the attention of rights.
18. Include transparency mechanisms that make the data subject explicitly aware that processing is taking place.
19. Include mechanisms that allow the data subject to suspend processing under certain conditions.
20. Clearly inform users how to appeal a refusal to exercise a right.
21. Limit as much as possible the level of detail used in the processing of personal data.
22. Limiting the extent of the processing so that it does not involve data of subjects considered vulnerable (elderly, minors, persons with disabilities, etc.).
23. Limit access to personal data that data processors must manage.

7.3. Data Retention

The personal data will be stored until the project's end in case BIOservicES needs to contact participants again for new samplings, additional surveys, participation in events, etc. In sum, BIOservicES will not retain information from individuals and locations or keep it private. The consortium will treat all personal information connected to the audience response data with the highest level of consideration, courtesy, privacy and ethical practices. BIOservicES will not share any of the critical data related to confidentiality with anybody outside the research team. Concerning possible publications resulting from participation in the study, BIOservicES will not identify subjects by name or other details that might facilitate access to names, such as experimental sites geographical coordinates.

7.4. Data Destruction

All data provided by any participant will be destroyed upon request. In addition, personal data will be destroyed immediately after the project is finished. However, the project coordinator will retain pseudonymised scientific non-personal data for an embargo period of 5 years after the project ends. Data Management Plan will detail what type of data the BIOservicES project generates, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be stored.

8. Personal data transfer between EU and non-EU countries

Personal data will be transferred from EU to non-EU countries or international organisations.

The non-EU countries Switzerland, USA and UK, participating in BIOservicES, will follow the same procedure for collection, protection and destruction of the data, as EU countries will do, which means collecting the information by stakeholders, pseudonymising personal data by giving a code number to each participant, securely saving that information, and following the BIOservicES rules for data storage and destruction.

Neither EU countries nor non-EU countries will share personal data collected from stakeholders with any other partner or third countries. The personal data will be kept securely stored without the possibility of external access. The only information that will be transferred from EU to non-EU countries and vice-versa will be scientific information that will be necessary to analyse the data and the impact of the progress of the project in each biogeographic region, but these data will be already pseudonymised, which makes impossible to identify or relate any participant to the collected data.

Anyway, **all the BIOservicES partners** will ensure that all ethics issues related to activities in the project are addressed in compliance with ethical principles, the applicable international and national laws, and the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement. This includes the already identified ethics issues and any additional issues that may emerge during the project. If any substantial new ethics issues arise, the BIOservicES consortium will inform the granting authority.

Anyway, in case that during the project's development, the transfer of personal data between EU and non-EU countries or international organisations

becomes necessary, such transfer will be according to Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. It will comply with the country's laws in which the data were collected.

9. Activities undertaken in non-EU countries.

Activities undertaken outside the EU, in non-EU countries, will be legal according to GDPR and the non-EU country.

As far as Spain is the project's coordinator, it has been established as the referential EU country to follow for non-EU countries concerning the legality of the activities undertaken in the non-EU countries Switzerland, USA and UK under the umbrella of the BIOservicES project. The three of them have asked permission from their respective institutions/organizations, confirming that they have it to participate in the assigned activities under the frame of BIOservicES.

The partners from Switzerland, USA and UK will follow the EU rules in the activities undertaken in the BIOservicES project, and sent the files to the coordinator, which will keep them and provide to the European Commission in case it requests those files.

Switzerland will collect and send soil samples to the EU country Spain, and the EU countries will send soil samples to Switzerland and USA. However, there will be no transfer of samples between non-EU countries.

10. Materials imported to / exported from the EU.

The materials imported to the EU consist of soil samples collected from the experimental sites of the BIOservicES project in Switzerland. The materials exported from the EU to Switzerland and USA consist of soil samples collected from all the experimental sites of the BIOservicES project. The permits for their export are issued only after the samples have been checked for infections by each national service. Therefore, when the import/export authorizations, as required by national/EU legislation are issued, copies of those authorizations will be kept on file (after reception confirmation is submitted) and provided to the Agency upon request. As all the countries will send the soil samples to the Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT) from Spain (an EU country), we will follow the requirements of this country to import soil from non-EU countries listed in Annex VI of R(EU) 2019/2072. The competence lies with the autonomous communities, in this case, the Región de Murcia Government.

11. Ethical considerations and compliance for the transfer of biological material under the Nagoya Protocol in BIOServicES

The BIOServicES project involves the collection, transfer, and analysis of soil biological and genetic material from both EU and non-EU sources, notably Switzerland. Given this international scope, it is essential to ensure full compliance with the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) and its implementation in the EU under Regulation (EU) No. 511/2014. These legal frameworks seek to promote the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and safeguard the sovereign rights of provider countries. This section provides a comprehensive overview of the regulatory obligations and ethical considerations associated with the transfer and use of genetic material in BIOServicES. It details the legal provisions, their interpretation in the project's context, the clarifications obtained from relevant authorities, and the operational implications across the work packages.

The Nagoya Protocol, adopted under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), establishes the international legal basis for the fair and equitable sharing of benefits derived from the utilization of genetic resources. The European Union has implemented this protocol through Regulation (EU) No. 511/2014.

Under Article 3 of the Regulation, 'utilisation' is defined as research and development on the genetic and/or biochemical composition of genetic resources. Article 4 introduces a due diligence obligation, requiring users to seek, obtain, and maintain information on the legal provenance of the genetic resources they use. However, Annex II clarifies that activities aimed exclusively at taxonomic identification (including sequencing not intended to explore functional properties) are not considered 'utilisation'.

In BIOServicES, partners who received soil samples from Switzerland engaged proactively with their respective National Focal Points (NFPs). The Swiss NFP confirmed that the activities conducted under the Project (including DNA sequencing) were strictly taxonomic and did not qualify as 'utilisation' within the meaning of the Regulation. Consequently, access authorisation was deemed unnecessary, and the requirement to establish Prior Informed Consent (PIC) or Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT) was waived. To ensure legal certainty and good practice, all samples are sterilised by autoclaving after analysis to prevent any potential misuse. This interpretative position, endorsed by the Swiss competent authority and grounded in EU law, provides the basis for the compliance framework adopted in BIOServicES.

WP	Task(s)	ABS Implications	Normative Source
WP2 – Soil biodiversity	T2.1–T2.6	Sequencing of Swiss soil biota post-2014 may fall under ABS scope.	Art. 3, 4, 12 (Reg.); Art. 5, 6 (Nagoya)
WP3 – Data & Modelling	T3.1–T3.3	Integration of taxonomic sequences into predictive AI models.	Art. 5, 10
WP4 – Ecosystem services valuation	T4.4	Use of upstream data; no direct genetic R&D.	Art. 5
WP7 – Management	T7.1–T7.2	Coordination of documentation and ethics oversight.	Art. 4
WP8 – Ethics	All relevant	Central oversight of Nagoya compliance across project.	Art. 4, 7

Table 1. Application to BIOServicES Work Packages

To ensure ongoing compliance with national ABS regulations, the following National Focal Points (NFPs) are relevant for the BIOServicES project:

Country	NFP Institution	Contact Email	Telephone
Switzerland	State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO)	abs@seco.admin.ch	+41 58 464 08 08
Spain	Directorate General for Biodiversity, MITECO	abs@miteco.es	+34 91 453 53 00
European Union	European Commission – ABS Secretariat	RTD-ABS@ec.europa.eu	+32 2 299 11 11

Table 2. National Focal Point (NFP) contacts

These NFPs serve as the primary contacts for clarifications on national ABS legislation, confirmation of scope, and formal communications regarding access and benefit-sharing responsibilities.

